

The Influence of Transactional Leadership of Police Commissioned Officers and Quality of Work Life on Organizational Commitment among Police Non-Commissioned Officers

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Abstract:- The aim of the study is to determine the influence of transactional leadership and quality of work life on organizational commitment among police non-commissioned officers. This study used quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlational technique. Adapted survey questionnaires were administered randomly to 260 non-commissioned police officers of Cotabato City Police Office, Police Regional Office, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region, Philippines. Findings show very high levels of transactional leadership, quality of work life, and organizational commitment. It also revealed that there were significant relationships between transactional leadership and organizational commitment and between quality of work life and organizational commitment. However, only quality of work life significantly influenced organizational commitment. With this result, it is recommended that Cotabato City Police Office, PRO BAR, may sustain a very high level of organizational commitment in achieving the goals of the PNP by enhancing transactional leadership practices in terms of laissez faire leadership among commissioned police officers and quality of work life specifically on relation and cooperation among non-commissioned officers by initiating trainings and other intervention schemes.

Keywords:- criminal justice, transactional leadership, quality of work life, organizational commitment, commissioned and non-commissioned police officers, Bangsamoro Autonomous Region, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

In organizational commitment, low levels of staff morale have been identified as an issue (De Cottis & Summers, 2017), which has resulted in decreasing measures of self-sacrifice and compliance (Schappe, 2018). In other words, low levels of organizational commitment among workers may cause outsiders to see the organization in an unfavorable light, limiting the company's capacity to recruit high-quality people (Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 2012). As a result, a company that does not have devoted employees would eventually collapse (Chen, 2016).

Furthermore, the issue of organizational commitment, which is associated with high retention rates, is a problem that is encountered in law enforcement, as well as many other fields of employment. Turnover is a constant issue in organizations, whether they are in the public or private sectors, in this age of globalization. Retention is a prevalent problem in every kind and size of company, as well as at every level of the organization's hierarchy (Cascio, 2011). With regard to the United States, a number of studies have shown that up to 50% of new workers quit their jobs within the first five years after beginning their careers. Some of the finest and brightest among the newcomers tend to be the ones who are most likely to quit for a variety of reasons, including inadequate remuneration and benefits, a lack of management support, and other factors.

Additionally, the NCTAF, or National Commission on Employment and Americas Future, reported in 2011 that about a third of all new workers quit their positions within three years, and nearly half depart within five years (Henke, 2010). If the high staff turnover is not addressed immediately, it will almost certainly cause damage and hinder the operations of businesses in the long term. In Britain and other areas of Europe, worker attrition and turnover has been raised to the level of a national catastrophe as its citizens migrate to higher-paying jobs in more developed Asian economies, which are considered to be accessible in these countries.

However, according to Hogan et al. (2016), continuance performance is important to the success of any establishment because it is an important job outcome in and of itself due to its demonstrated effect on positive task attitudes and behavior. Organizational commitment is also important for the success of any entity because it is an important job outcome in and of itself due to its proved influence on optimistic work-related attitudes (Gregersen & Black, 2012). As a result of its unique nature, the law enforcement is reliant on its employees' devotion to do their duties in what may be a chaotic, uncertain, and difficult environment (Brodeur, 2018). The image & substance of police also highlights the significance of pride with in service, ethical work practices, and a strong sense of community orientation; as a result, the organizational culture of force personnel is vital to the deployment of strategic and tactical resources.

Furthermore, transactional leadership is considered to be one of the most important antecedents of organizational commitment. According to organizational commitment (Davidmann, 2015), The method in which work gets conducted, the amount of employees' dedication to the institution, and the measure to which workers co-operate each other, executives, and the larger community are some of the elements that play a role in determining the influence that any organization has. On the other hand, as Radia (2013) points out, the quality of one's work life has a negligible impact on public service quality of work life, but it has a significant impact on organizational commitment, as evidenced by the fact that it has a positive correlation with work engagement. Furthermore, organizational commitment has an indirect impact on the performance of government good, but it has an indirectly effect on the performance of civil administration via job satisfaction. Furthermore, both the quality of one's working life and the dedication of an organization have a little impact on public service performance, although both might make direct contributions to it via one's job performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Descriptive-correlational techniques were utilized in this quantitative analysis. As a random selection of a broad population is drawn from a survey, more data can be collected using this approach. Krathwohl (1993) argued that descriptive-correlational research has three basic purposes: to describe, explain, and verify results. Polit, and Hungler (2009) added that Approaches that are intuitive, panoramic, intuitive, and methodology are examples of descriptive-correlational research. These methods are used to comprehend, analyze, and characterize a phenomenon or environment in order to construct a theory about it, while Deci (2005) stated that it is a systematic, the subjective method is one that is used to explain the events of one's life and to give them meaning. This perspective is most often connected with vocabulary, terminology, and sensations, as well as measures, analytics, and numerical numbers.

The researcher sent an official letter to dean of Graduate School, signed by the research advisor, requesting permission to perform the study. Letters towards the City Director of Cotabato City Police Office were also written to the research advisor, requesting authorization to distribute survey questionnaires to policemen in his area.

The survey questionnaire was delivered to the respondents once the researcher obtained the relevant approvals. Survey questionnaires were collected and tallied by a researcher under the supervision of a statistician after they had been administered. The findings were then examined and interpreted in accordance with the research question. On the second semester of SY 2021-2022, data was gathered.

A modified survey questionnaire that had been accepted and changed by the researcher and had been acquired from the internet served as the research instrument. With the advice of the research consultant, the researcher made modifications to the previously developed survey questionnaire. The questionnaire for the survey was broken into four (4) sections. The first section dealt with the demographic characteristics of those who answered the survey questions. The second, third, and fourth portions of the survey consisted of questions about the degree of transactional leadership, the quality of work life, and the level of organizational commitment, in that order.

The following scales were used to evaluate the degree of transactional leadership of the respondents:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Transactional leadership is always felt.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Transactional leadership is often felt.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Transactional leadership is sometimes felt.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Transactional leadership is seldom felt.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Transactional leadership is never felt.

Table 1

In the evaluation of level of quality of work life of the respondents, the following scales were used:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Quality of work life is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Quality of work life is often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Quality of work life is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Quality of work life is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Quality of work life is never manifested.

Table 2

The accompanying scales were used in the assessment of the respondents' degree of organizational commitment:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Organizational commitment is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Organizational commitment is oftentimes manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Organizational commitment is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Organizational commitment is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Organizational commitment is never manifested.

Table 3

The researcher conducted the survey using a technique known as stratified sampling, which is a kind of probability sampling that is employed in large samples. The components that make up the demographic are segmented into a number of unique groups or strata, and the elements that make up each division are comparable to one another in terms of a number of key criteria that are significant to the survey. In addition to this, stratification may be used to improve the effectiveness of a selection design in terms of both the expenses of the survey and the accuracy of the estimate. The use of stratified sampling in five important large-scale health surveys carried out in the United States and the United Kingdom is illustrative of the significance of this method of data collection in clinical settings. For these surveys, information on the stratification and sample techniques is given in depth (VL Parsons, 2014).

Criteria for a respondent to qualify are: must be a police officer presently assigned at Cotabato City Police office, PRO BAR, may be of any rank in the PNP organization, may be female or male in gender, of legal age, and a Filipino. Excluded respondents in the conduct of this study are: non-Uniformed personnel working in the PNP organization, Civilians in the Community, Retired PNP personnel, and PNP personnel outside Cotabato City Police Office. Those PNP personnel who are not willing to participate in the study because respondents are given free will to participate without any form of consequences, penalty or loss of benefits may withdraw from the study or refuses to answer the questionnaire.

Cotabato City Police Office, Police Regional Office Bangsamoro Autonomous Region (PRO BAR) is a former Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). The city is administratively part of Region 12, which is composed of the five provinces. For geographical, statistical and legislative purposes, it is grouped with the province of Maguindanao but still does belong to the BAR.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Transactional Leadership

Presented in this section is the analysis and interpretation of data based on responses gathered from the police officers of Cotabato City Police Office with regards to the influence of transactional leadership and quality of work life on organizational commitment thereat and the discussions of the influence of transactional leadership and employment balance depends on the level of motivation for employees of police officer and likewise, unveiled in this section are the correlations between transactional leadership and quality of work life on organizational commitment and the regression analysis of the influence transactional leadership and quality of work life on organizational commitment. Finally, complete content and organizational editing before formatting. Please take note of the following items when proofreading spelling and grammar:

Reflected in Table 4 is the level of transactional leadership manifested by the police officers in Cotabato City Police Office. The overall mean rating 4.26 with a standard deviation of 0.368 and described as very high which means the transactional leadership was always observed by the police officers. This also meant that police officer has a very high transactional leadership.

Further, the mean scores of the indicators of transactional leadership are revealed as follows: Contingency Pay, Management-by-Exception, and Laissez Faire Leadership were all given high ratings with a standard deviation of 0.507, 4.35 and 4.03, respectively, by a sample size of 320 people.

The very high level of transactional leadership of police officers in Cotabato City was due to the very high ratings of the respondents in terms of contingent rewards and management-by-exception. This means that PNP Commissioned Officers provide recognition rewards to subordinates when they reach their goals and if things are working, they are not trying to change anything.

The findings are aligned with the study of Odumeru and Ifeanyi (2013) that Transactional leadership is characterized by the establishment of criteria for rewarding following and

preserving the status quo as the primary actions associated with this leadership style.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Contingent Reward	0.507	4.41	Very High
Management-by-Exception	0.510	4.35	Very High
Laissez Faire Leadership	0.560	4.03	High
Overall	0.368	4.26	Very High

Table 4: Level of Transactional Leadership

B. Quality of Work Life

Depicted in Table 5 is the level of quality of work life of police officers of Cotabato City Police Office. The overall mean rating is 4.33 with a standard deviation of 0.346 as very high which meant that quality of work life was oftentimes observed by the police officers in Cotabato City Police Office. Also, this indicates that police officer has very high level of quality of work life.

The mean score of the indicators of quality of work life revealed as follows: Training and Development obtain a mean rating of 4.43 with a standard deviation of 0.494, described as very high; Job Satisfaction and Job Security a mean rating of 4.40 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.450; Compensation and Rewards a mean rating of 4.38 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.434; Facilities a mean rating of 4.36 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.561; Organization Culture and Climate a mean rating of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.399; Autonomy of Work a mean rating of 4.30 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.501; Adequacy of Resources a mean rating of 4.29 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.530; Work Environment a mean rating of 4.28 or very high with a

standard deviation of 0.428; and Relation and Cooperation a mean rating of 4.19 or high with a standard deviation of 0.448.

The very high degree of professional life quality of police officers in Cotabato City was being contributed by the very high mean ratings given by the respondents in all indicators except Relation and Cooperation which is high.

Further, the police officer in Cotabato City Police Office shows an excellent quality of work-related activities in the PNP organization because their work environment is being good and highly motivating because All departments are working together to achieve the overarching PNP objectives, the organization is also offering necessary training opportunities to execute the job successfully, as well as the perception that they are receiving enough and fair remuneration for the task that they accomplish, are two of the most important factors in employee retention.

The result was congruent with the statement of Jain and Thomas (2016) That employees who work in organizations that provide enough compensation, safe and healthy workplaces, legal task design, and the relevance of industry to society are more satisfied with their employment and their work lives than those who do not have these conditions.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Work Environment	0.428	4.28	Very High
Organization Culture and Climate	0.399	4.32	Very High
Relation and Cooperation	0.448	4.19	High
Training and Development	0.494	4.43	Very High
Compensation and Rewards	0.434	4.38	Very High
Facilities	0.561	4.36	Very High
Job Satisfaction and Job Security	0.450	4.40	Very High
Autonomy of Work	0.501	4.30	Very High
Adequacy of Resources	0.530	4.29	Very High
Overall	0.346	4.33	Very High

Table 5: Level of Quality of Work Life

C. Organizational Commitment

Highlighted in Table 6 is the level of organizational commitment of police officers in Cotabato City Police Office. The overall mean rating is 4.33 with a standard deviation of 0.393 described as very high which meant the organizational commitment is all the time observed by the police officers. This also implied that the commitment in the PNP of the police officers in Cotabato City Police Office is very high.

The mean scores of the indicators of organizational commitment were unveiled as follows: There were three types of commitment measured: Affective Commitment received a

mean rating of 4.35, which was very high, and Continuance Commitment received a mean rating of 4.32, which was very high, and Standard Deviation of 0.44; and Normative Commitment received a mean rating of 4.33, which was also very high, and Standard Deviation of 0.45.

The very high level of organizational commitment of police officers in Cotabato City Police Office was due to the very high mean ratings given by the respondents to all indicators of organizational commitment.

Further, the police officers of this city present the importance of organizational commitment within the PNP, that

the organization has a great deal of personal meaning for them and it would be very hard for them to leave in the organization right now, even if they wanted to. And one of the major reasons they continue to work for this organization is believing that being loyal and having a sense of ethical duty to stay are crucial factors in every relationship.

The findings of this research are consistent with the claims made by Mowday, Steers, and Porter (2009), who assert that conscientiousness may be characterized as a high

interest to continue performing or functioning for an entity. The same may be said about the statements made by Lee, Law, and Bobko (2009) This means that all personnel must pledge their allegiance to the business and work together to achieve all of its stated goals, objectives, and equipment. And finally, the study is aligned in the statement of Allen & Meyer, (2010) that extremely devoted individuals are less likely to abandon their jobs than other types of employees.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Commitment	0.444	4.35	Very High
Continuance Commitment	0.442	4.32	Very High
Normative Commitment	0.455	4.33	Very High
Overall	0.393	4.33	Very High

Table 6: Level of Organizational Commitment

D. Significance on the Relationship between the Transactional Leadership and Organizational Commitment

Shown in the Table 7 is the data on the correlation of independent variable transactional leadership to the dependent variable organizational commitment. The overall result revealed that with an overall r-value of .349 and a p-value of 0.000, which is 0.05 level of significance, transactional leader has a substantial link with organizational commitment. Commitment within an institution is strongly correlated with the kind of administration in place.

A correlation between contingent compensation, as an indication of transactional leadership, and the dependent variable, task performance, was found to be .234 and 0.05, respectively, indicating that the relationship is significant. If you take into account the indicators of management by exception and commitment to the organization, the overall r-value is .318 and the p<0.05 level of significance remains the same, and if you take into consideration the indicators of laissez-faire leaders inspire and motivate, the overall r-value is .188 and the level of significance remains the same, you have significant results in both cases as well. All probability values indicated statistically significant associations, as seen by this data.

Meanwhile, the overall result revealed that organizational commitment has a significant relationship to transactional leadership with the overall r-value of .349 and p-value of 0.000, which is <0.05 level of significance, thus, significant.

It was discovered that the dependent variable, task behavior, was linked with the emotional commitment indicator, and that the total r-value was .254, and that the significance level was 0.05, indicating that it was significant. It was discovered that the independent variable, transactional, was connected with a continuing commitment indicator with an overall coefficient of correlation of .381 and a p-value of 0.05.; still, significant and lastly, when normative commitment indicator was correlated to the independent variable, transactional leadership, the overall r-value is .286 and p<0.05; likewise, significant.

The current study revealed that transactional leadership police officers is significantly related with their organizational commitment which is aligned with the study of Jackson (2013) that the favorable association between contingent compensation and employee commitment is consistent with the beneficial effect on employee commitment. Result of the study is also parallel with the statement of Lowe (2014) which identifies strong leadership including transactional is one of the most important characteristics of a healthy organization.

Furthermore, as stated by the Canadian Council for Integrated Health (2012), Being able to lead effectively is one of the most critical qualities a person can possess of a healthy workplace, and without strong commitment from the top, workplace health cannot advance. However, Bass (1990), found a that among the variables examined, there was a negative association between emotional, normative, and continuous commitment, and the effectiveness of transactional leadership.

Transactional Leadership	Organizational Commitment			
	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	Overall
Contingent Reward	.217* (0.000)	.198* (0.001)	.202* (0.001)	.234* (0.000)
Management-by-Exception	.239* (0.000)	.349* (0.000)	.253* (0.000)	.318* (0.000)
Laissez Faire Leadership	.089 (0.153)	.256* (0.000)	.152* (0.014)	.188* (0.002)
Overall	.254* (0.000)	.381* (0.000)	.286* (0.000)	.349* (0.000)

Table 7: Significance on the Relationship between the Transactional Leadership and Organizational Commitment

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

E. Significance on the Relationship between the Quality of Work life and Organizational Commitment

Shown in Table 8 is the data on the correlation of the independent variable to the dependent variable. The overall result revealed that work-life balance has a relation to loyalty to the group with the overall r-value of .689 and p-value of 0.000, which is <0.05 level of significance, thus, significant. When work environment indicator was parallel with the dependent variable organizational pledge, the overall r-value is .478 and p<0.05; hence, significant. When organization culture and climate indicator was interconnected to the dependent variable organizational promise, the overall r-value is .438 and p<0.05; still significant.

When relation and cooperation indicator was linked with the dependent variable organizational commitment, the overall r-value is .460 and p<0.05; still important. When training and development indicator was connected to the dependent variable organizational commitment, the overall r-value is .384 and p<0.05; still significant. When compensation and rewards indicator was correlated with the dependent variable institutional pledge, the overall r-value is .590 and p value is lesser than the value of 0.05; still significant. When facilities indicator was parallel with the dependent variable group devotion, the overall r-value is .441 and p<0.05; still significant. When job satisfaction and job security indicator was correlated to the dependent variable institution dedication, the overall r-value is .627 and p<0.05; still important. When autonomy of work indicator was connected with the dependent variable organizational commitment, the overall r-value is .586 and p<0.05; still significant and finally, when adequacy of resources indicator was correlated to the dependent variable

organizational commitment, the overall r-value is .550 and p<0.05; likewise significant.

Moreover, that quality organizational commitment has a connection that is vital to a happy and healthy work existence with the overall r-value of .689 and p-value of 0.000, which is <0.05 level of significance, thus, significant. When affective commitment indicator was correlated with the factor to be considered which is quality of life in work, the overall r-value is .663 and p<0.05; hence, important. When continuance commitment indicator was link with the manipulated variable quality of work life the overall r-value is .546 and p<0.05; still, significant and lastly, when normative commitment indicator was correlated with the explanatory variable career harmony, the overall r-value is .606 and p<0.05; likewise, significant.

The current study revealed There is a considerable link between the quality of one's working life and the dedication of the institution of police officer in Cotabato City Police Office. It only means that the police officer's quality of work life is related with organizational commitment. In a singular state, indicators such as Work Environment, Organization Culture and Climate, Relation and Cooperation, Training and Development, Compensation and Rewards, Facilities, Job Satisfactory and Job Security, Autonomy of Work and Adequacy of Resources are correlated with organizational commitment, Level of job satisfaction and work motivation have a clear association. This study is aligned in the statement of Daud (2010) to explore the relationship between career synergy and group devotion amongst employees in Malaysian firms; it was found that there was a meaningful relationship between quality of work life and organizational commitment.

Quality of Work Life	Organizational Commitment			
	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	Overall
Work Environment	.450* (0.000)	.404* (0.000)	.406* (0.000)	.478* (0.000)
Organization Culture and Climate	.444* (0.000)	.384* (0.000)	.326* (0.000)	.438* (0.000)
Relation and Cooperation	.459* (0.000)	.352* (0.000)	.400* (0.000)	.460* (0.000)
Training and Development	.366* (0.000)	.297* (0.000)	.349* (0.000)	.384* (0.000)
Compensation and Rewards	.540* (0.000)	.499* (0.000)	.516* (0.000)	.590* (0.000)
Facilities	.412* (0.000)	.306* (0.000)	.442* (0.000)	.441* (0.000)
Job Satisfaction and Job Security	.593* (0.000)	.514* (0.000)	.544* (0.000)	.627* (0.000)
Autonomy of Work	.548* (0.000)	.487* (0.000)	.509* (0.000)	.586* (0.000)
Adequacy of Resources	.570* (0.000)	.390* (0.000)	.488* (0.000)	.550* (0.000)
Overall	.663* (0.000)	.546* (0.000)	.606* (0.000)	.689* (0.000)

Table 8: Significance on the Relationship between the Quality of Work life and Organizational Commitment

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

F. Influence of Predictor Variables on Organizational Commitment

Organizational Commitment (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	.863	.250	3.447	.001
Transactional Leadership (TL)	.035	.038	.695	.488
Quality of Work Life (QWL)	.673	.764	13.180	.000
R	.690			
R2	.476			
F	116.695			
P	.000			

Table 9: The Extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Organizational Commitment

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based from the finding of the study, the researcher came up the following salient conclusions;

The level of transactional leadership, quality of job and institutional dedication are all very high. Results also revealed that transactional leadership and quality of employment positively correlated and have significant relationships to administrative devotion. However, only quality of task has influence to structural pledge. The results proved the contention of Gnanayudam and Dharmasiri (2007) Employee participation and allegiance are directly linked to the quality of the effort put forth. And also, It was found in research carried out by Daud (2010) to investigate the link between good of workforce and sociocultural perseverance amongst employees working in Malaysian firms that there was a useful relationship between the level of job but rather governmental commitments. The purpose of the study was to determine whether or not there was a connection between the two.

Considering of the foregoing findings and conclusion of this study, the researcher put forward the following recommendations;

Based on the results of the study, it is recommended that Cotabato City Police Office, PRO BAR may sustain a very high level of hierarchical commitments in achieving the goal of the PNP by enhancing transactional leadership in terms of laissez faire leadership through being content to let subordinates continue working in the same way as always and not caring much what the subordinates are doing unless the work is absolutely essential. Also, a very high level of institutional dedication may sustain by improving quality of work-related activities in terms of relation and cooperation by having a harmonious relationship between and among

colleagues and by having a very cordial relationship with immediate head.

Furthermore, PNP may initiates programs/trainings/seminars that will improve the transactional leadership and quality of task of police officers of Cotabato City Police Office, PRO BAR in relation to laissez faire leadership and relation and cooperation, respectively.

Finally, it is also recommended that studies on the other factors that influence the institutional dedication of police officers may be conducted.

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